

HeatResilientCity II - work package 2.2: Influence of regional and urban climate on indoor overheating – Building models, simulation boundary condition and their variations

Geometric, structural and technical building parameters of the considered multi-residential “Gründerzeithaus” (GZH) and large-panel construction (LPC) building

Component	LPC building	GZH building
Exterior walls	<p>basement: 15 cm reinforced concrete / 0.4 cm sealing / 10 cm exterior insulation ($U = 0.3 \frac{W}{m^2K}$)</p> <p>level 1 to 6: 14 cm reinforced concrete / 6 cm insulation / 6 cm reinforced concrete / 10 cm exterior insulation ($U = 0.2 \frac{W}{m^2K}$)</p> <p>attic: 11 cm reinforced concrete / 10 cm insulation ($U = 0.3 \frac{W}{m^2K}$)</p> <p>Surface: shortwave reflectance = 0.5</p>	<p>level 1 & 2: 1.5 cm render / 51 cm brick wall / 1.5 cm render ($U = 0.84 \frac{W}{m^2K}$)</p> <p>level 3 & 4: 1.5 cm render / 38 cm brick wall / 1.5 cm render ($U = 1.07 \frac{W}{m^2K}$)</p> <p>attic: 1.5 cm exterior rendering / 24 cm brick wall / 6 cm extruded polystyrene (XPS) as interior insulation / 1 cm interior rendering ($U = 0.43 \frac{W}{m^2K}$)</p> <p>Surface: shortwave reflectance = 0.5</p>
Interior walls	<p>Concrete walls 4 cm to 15 cm ($U = 4.3 - 5.3 \frac{W}{m^2K}$)</p> <p>Drywalls 7.5 cm and 10 cm with 1.25 cm plaster on both sides ($U = 0.36 - 0.47 \frac{W}{m^2K}$)</p> <p>Some brick walls 17.5 cm and 24 cm with 1 cm rendering on both sides ($U = 2.5 - 2.87 \frac{W}{m^2K}$)</p>	<p>mainly 1.5 cm render / 25 cm brick walls / 1.5 cm render ($U = 1.57 \frac{W}{m^2K}$)</p> <p>some drywalls (2.5 cm plasterboard / 5 cm insulation / 2.5 cm plasterboard, ($U = 0.57 \frac{W}{m^2K}$)</p> <p>in attic only drywalls</p> <p>Gabel end wall: 1.25 cm plasterboard / 6 cm interior XPS insulation / 1.5 cm render / 38 cm brick wall / 1.5 cm render ($U = 0.39 \frac{W}{m^2K}$)</p>

Basement ceiling	10 cm insulation / 14 cm concrete / 2.5 cm insulation / 5 cm anhydrite screed / 0.35 cm flooring ($U = 0.27 \frac{W}{m^2K}$)	15 cm concrete / 6 cm XPS insulation / 5 cm screed / 0.3 cm footstep sound insulation / flooring ($U = 0.48 \frac{W}{m^2K}$)
Ceilings	14 cm concrete / 3 cm anhydrite screed / 0.35 cm flooring ($U = 3.62 \frac{W}{m^2K}$)	wooden beam ceilings: 2.5 cm plasterboard / 3 cm air gap / 2 cm wood / 3 cm air gap / 2 cm wood / 8 cm sand/gravel / 2 cm air gap / 2 cm wood / 1 cm insulation / 2 cm dry screed / flooring ($U = 0.63 \frac{W}{m^2K}$)
Top-floor ceiling	14 cm insulation / 6 cm insulation / 14 cm concrete ($U = 0.22 \frac{W}{m^2K}$)	-
Roof	Flat roof (cold roof) of reinforced concrete Surface: dark grey (shortwave reflectance = 0.092)	gable roof with dormers 14 cm mineral wool insulation between rafters and 2.5 cm plasterboard on the inside ($U = 0.21 \frac{W}{m^2K}$) Surface: brown tiles (shortwave reflectance = 0.291)
Windows	triple insulation glazing ($U_w = 0.7 \frac{W}{m^2K}$ and $g = 0.51$) frame ratios: 0.3 – 0.64, average 0.39	double insulation glazing ($U_w = 1.8 \frac{W}{m^2K}$, $g = 0.6$) frame ratios: 0.1 – 0.35, average 0.3

Additional simulations of the LPC building with double glazing ($U_w = 1.3 \frac{W}{m^2K}$ and $g = 0.7$) have the file extension *_doubleglazing*.

Boundary conditions for building performance simulation

- Climate:
 - All climate files are supplied in the folder *climate files*. The files cover
 - years with an average present summer based on the measurement data and calculations in the related repository (Kriesten, 2023),
 - a year from current measurement data that can be considered as an average future summer,
 - the years with an average present and future summer with consideration of urban climate and
 - Test Reference Years (TRY) according to DIN 4108-2 (DIN, 2013)
- for each region mentioned in the table below.

Region	Dresden, Germany	Hamburg, Germany	Köln, Germany	Stuttgart, Germany	Potsdam, Germany
Latitude	51.128 N	53.633 N	50.865 N	48.828 N	52.381 N
Longitude	13.754 E	9.988 E	7.158 E	9.200 E	13.062 E
Height above sea level	227 m	14 m	92 m	314 m	81 m
Time Zone	UTC+1				

- Location settings for the climate are chosen according to the considered regions and their associated weather stations.
- Wind measurement height is set to 10 m (due to the standard measurement height of the considered meteorological stations).
- For simulations with TRY the location settings for the climate are chosen according to the associated weather station of the TRY:

TRY	TRY2010_4	TRY2010_12
Latitude	52.381 N	49.517 N
Longitude	13.067 E	8.55 E
Height above sea level	81 m	96 m
Time zone	UTC+1	

- Location (building location):
 - The building location is set equal to the regions in climate location.
 - For simulations with the TRY climate, the building location is also set equal to the considered region (Dresden, Hamburg, Köln, Stuttgart, Potsdam) NOT to the coordinates of the TRY.
- Wind profile:
 - IDA ICE integrated power law profile: $v_w(h) = v_m * A_0 * \left(\frac{h}{h_m}\right)^{A_{exp}}$
 - h_m measurement height of wind speed (climate data)
 - v_m measured wind speed at h_m
 - A_0 coefficient for v_m
 - A_{exp} power law exponent in general empirically derived
 - For simulations without urban climate, the standard 'IDA ICE Airport' profile is considered ($A_0 = 1.0, A_{exp} = 0.15$).
 - For simulations with TRY, the standard IDA ICE suburban profile is considered ($A_0 = 0.67, A_{exp} = 0.25$).
 - For simulation with consideration of urban climate, the exponent is adjusted depending on the city structure:

City	Dresden, Germany	Hamburg, Germany	Köln, Germany	Stuttgart, Germany	Potsdam, Germany
A₀	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
A_{exp}	0.301	0.392	0.392	0.333	0.301

- Shading objects:
 - Shading due to balconies is taken into account.
 - No internal or external sun protection in the basic model (without adaptation measures) is considered.
- A thermal bridge loss coefficient related to all surfaces of the building envelope of $0.10 \frac{W}{m^2K}$ for the GZH building and $0.05 \frac{W}{m^2K}$ for the LPC building was assumed.
- The building air tightness related to all component surfaces (weighted by building envelope surface) is defined by the n_{50} value (air exchange rate coefficient at 50 Pa pressure difference) of $4 h^{-1}$ (DIN, 2017).
- Assumed ventilation:
 - Windows tilted during the night (from 10 pm to 7 am) and fully opened in the morning (7 am to 8 am) and in the evening (8 pm to 10 pm) when the indoor air temperature is higher

than 22 °C and cooler than the outdoor air temperature. Balcony door of LPC is just tilted (from 8 pm to 8 am). This window-opening behaviour is based on window ventilation profiles derived from surveys (Schiela and Schünemann, 2021).

- During the day, the windows remain closed (from 8 am to 8 pm).
- In the basement and staircase windows are closed all the time.
- Room doors are closed all the time.
- Both BPS tools consider wind and temperature gradient-driven air exchange through windows by simplified pressure coefficients (for more details see (Schünemann et al., 2021)).
- Internal heat gains:
 - $100 \frac{W}{m^2d}$ based on (DIN, 2013) $\rightarrow 4.17 \frac{W}{m^2h}$ for each room.
 - Internal gains in the staircase, basement, attic/gallery and cold roof are set to 0.
 - No additional gains by occupants, light or other equipment.
- Simulation period:
 - Simulation period from 01.04. to 31.10. with a preconditioning phase of 1 month.

Building model variations (considered heat adaptation measures (AM))

Adaptation measures	LPC building	GZH building
AM 1	External shading ($g_m = 0.2$, $T_m = 0.15$, $U_m = 1.0$) on all windows, which are not shaded by balconies. Shading is drawn all the time.	Mechanical ventilation system with 1 h^{-1} (1 air change per hour) in attic floor bathrooms. External shading on the west side ($g_m = 0.2$, $T_m = 0.15$, $U_m = 1.0$) and internal shading ($g_m = 0.6$, $T_m = 0.2$, $U_m = 1.0$) on the east side, both in the forth and attic floor.
AM 2	Night ventilation (8 pm to 8 am) with fully opened windows in the top floor.	Night ventilation (8 pm to 8 am) with fully opened windows in the attic floor.
AM 3	Like AM 2 with cross ventilation.	Like AM 2 with cross ventilation.

Literature and related data

DIN, 2017. DIN EN 16798-7: Energetische Bewertung von Gebäuden - Lüftung von Gebäuden - Teil 7: Berechnungsmethoden zur Bestimmung der Luftvolumenströme in Gebäuden einschließlich Infiltration (Modul M5-5); Deutsche Fassung EN 16798-7:2017, DIN EN 16798-7: Energetische Bewertung von Gebäuden - Lüftung von Gebäuden. Beuth Verlag, Berlin.

DIN, 2013. DIN 4108-2:2013-02, Wärmeschutz und Energie-Einsparung in Gebäuden Teil 2: Mindestanforderungen an den Wärmeschutz. Beuth Verlag, Berlin.

Kriesten, T. F., 2023. HeatResilientCity II - work package 2.2: Influence of regional and urban climate on indoor overheating - Characteristic annual data and average present years.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.8245936>

Schiela, D., Schünemann, C., 2021. Window Ventilation Behavior for Overheating Evaluation: Residents' Survey and Derived Ventilation Profiles. *Int. J. Built Environ. Sustain.* 8, 121–133.
<https://doi.org/10.11113/ijbes.v8.n3.852>

Schünemann, C., Schiela, D., Ortlepp, R., 2021. How window ventilation behaviour affects the heat resilience in multi-residential buildings. *Build. Environ.* 202, 107987.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.buildenv.2021.107987>